

Synthesis of recyclable water-soluble polymeric chelators

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Facile synthesis of water-soluble poly(*N*-isopropyl acrylamide) bound chelators is reported. These polymeric chelators have a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) and quantitatively phase-separate on heating. Their utility in metal removal and recycling is demonstrated with hydroxamic acid as ligand and Fe³⁺ as metal ion.

Sequestration of trace metals using water-soluble polymers is recently reported by Bergbreiter *et al.*¹. These reactive polymers not only chelate the metal ions but they are also capable of extracting them quantitatively. This is possible because these polymers with poly(*N*-isopropyl acrylamide) (PNIPAM) backbone have lower critical solution temperature (LCST) of 30–32° and hence they quantitatively phase-separate from their aqueous solutions on heating above LCST. Bergbreiter *et al.* demonstrated metal sequestration and the subsequent extraction of metal by anchoring chelating units onto the poly(*N*-isopropyl acrylamide) backbone using Winnik's copolymer² of *N*-isopropyl acrylamide and *N*-acryloxy succinimide. This strategy of functionalisation of PNIPAM has a problem of purification because the displaced *N*-hydroxy succinimide remains partly suspended or partly solubilised in reaction mixtures.

In this communication, we report a new strategy to overcome the above mentioned difficulty by creating polymeric chelators from copolymers of *N*-isopropyl acrylamide and commercially available 2-vinyl-4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazoline-5-one, commonly referred to as vinyl azalactone (VAL). This copolymer is efficiently functionalised by opening azalactone ring by amino terminated ligands. In solution, this facile reaction is quantitative with no by-products. We have demonstrated the ease of anchoring amino terminated ligands and the utility of these functionalised polymers for metal sequestration.

Results and discussion

We synthesized copolymer (1) from *N*-isopropyl acrylamide and vinyl azalactone (8 : 2) using AIBN as an initiator in *t*-butanol. The IR spectrum of (1) showed a prominent stretch for carbonyl of azalactone at 1814 cm⁻¹ and carbonyl of amide at 1646 cm⁻¹. The methyl groups of

azalactone unit appeared at δ 2.13 in the PMR spectrum. Molecular weight by viscosity measurement² was found to be in the range of $M_v = 5 \times 10^5$ ($k = 9.59 \times 10^{-3}$ and $a = 0.65$). Unfortunately, due to broad signals, PMR spectrum was not of any help in ascertaining the mole ratio of monomers in (1) vis-à-vis the feed ratio. However, the relative mole ratio of *N*-isopropyl acrylamide to vinyl azalactone could be easily determined by reacting azalactone units of (1) with excess of UV-absorbing benzylamine and after isolation of polymer bound benzylamine, the free amine was estimated by either UV-spectroscopy or HPLC. Using this analytical method the actual mole ratio of the monomers was found to be quite close to the feed ratio. Alternatively, the monomer ratio in the copolymer can be determined by simple titrimetry after opening the azalactone ring by a diamine (see synthesis of (4) in the Experimental).

The amino terminated hydroxamic acid (2) was reacted with copolymer (1) by stirring the mixture of reactants in dry THF at 50° for 15 h. The completion of this reaction was confirmed by total disappearance of carbonyl stretch of lactone. The functionalised polymer (3) was then precipitated by pouring the reaction mixture into hexane and was subsequently purified by redissolving it into water and reprecipitating by heating the aqueous solution above its LCST.

The amino terminated hydroxamic acid (2) was synthesized by a four step procedure described by Bergbreiter *et al.*¹. *O*-Benzyl hydroxylamine was coupled with the Boc-protected amino hexanoic acid in the presence of 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole (CDI) to give Boc-6-amino-hexano-*O*-benzyl hydroxamic acid in 86% yield. Boc removal with trifluoroacetic acid and subsequent hydrolysis of this coupled product gave trifluoro acetate salt

of amino terminated hydroxamic acid (**2**).

As an alternative to this rather lengthy and expensive route to load hydroxamic acid unit onto PNIPAM backbone, we developed a short inexpensive and high yielding synthesis of a cationic polymeric chelator (**5**) containing hydroxamic groups as shown in Scheme 1. The azalactone units of copolymer (**1**) were opened quantitatively by primary amino groups of *N,N*-dimethyl propyl diamine. The tertiary nitrogen of this intermediate (**4**) was then quaternised by chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid (**6**) to give hydroxamic acid bound copolymer (**5**). The chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid was synthesized by debenzylating *O*-benzyl chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid that in turn was obtained from chloroacetyl chloride and *O*-benzyl hydroxylamine hydrochloride in quantitative yields.

Scheme 1

When copolymer (**5**) (200 mg) containing hydroxamic acid was treated with 25 ml of 15 ppm Fe^{3+} solution, red coloured hydroxamate complex was formed (0.867 absorbance at λ_{max} 463 nm). This polymer bound complex was precipitated by heating the solution above its LCST, leaving colourless supernatant. Quantitative chelation and phase-separation of polymer with sequestered metal ion (>99% recovery) was confirmed by adding chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid to the supernatant and measuring the absorbance at 463 nm.

The phase-separated, deep red coloured, polymeric chelator along with the bound Fe^{3+} ions was redissolved in fresh water and treated with excess of disodium EDTA. The

aqueous solution became colourless indicating regeneration of polymeric chelator (**5**) without the metal ion. The colourless solution was heated to recover the polymeric chelator (**5**) and was recycled for fresh chelation of Fe^{3+} . Thus, these water-soluble polymeric chelators were shown to function like soluble ion exchange resins for removal of trace metal ions from their aqueous solutions. We intend to make these kind of polymers with pre-organized ligands for selective sequestration of radioactive elements for remediation of radioactive waste³⁻⁵ of nuclear plants and the work in this direction is already in progress.

In summary, we have demonstrated a facile synthesis of polymeric chelators using commercially available monomers like *N*-isopropyl acrylamide and vinyl azalactone. The metal chelation efficiency and the recyclability of these polymeric chelators make them very cost effective.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial sources and used without purification unless otherwise stated. Vinyl azalactone was obtained from SNPE Chimie, France. All other chemicals were purchased from Aldrich. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained on a Varian Unity p300 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were reported as thin films between NaCl plates or as pressed KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer's FT-IR spectrometer. UV-Visible spectra were obtained using Varian's Cary 50 spectrometer. The monomeric chelators (**2,6**) and their precursors gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Synthesis of copolymer poly (NIPAM-*c*-VAL) (1) : *N*-Isopropyl acrylamide (NIPAM; 5.0 g, 44.25 mmol) and vinyl azalactone (VAL; 1.54 g, 11 mmol) were dissolved in *t*-butanol (80 ml) at 65° under nitrogen. A solution of AIBN (100 mg) in *t*-butanol (20 ml) was added to this solution. The reaction mixture was then stirred at 70° for 20 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated by removing 50% of solvent on a rotary evaporator. The concentrated solution thus obtained was poured into stirred hexane (500 ml) to precipitate the copolymer. The precipitated solid polymer was filtered and dried under high vacuum to yield 6.3 g of copolymer. The monomer mole ratio of 8 : 2 was ascertained by reacting *N,N*-dimethyl aminopropyl diamine as described in the synthesis of (**4**) in the Experimental. IR (KBr) 1651, 1814, 3299 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.0 to 1.27, 3.13, 3.97 (broad signals for polymer backbone and *N*-isopropyl groups) and 2.13 (broad tiny signal for dimethyl groups of azalactone unit). The molecular weight (M_v)

of this copolymer was determined to be 5×10^5 by viscometry².

Synthesis of Boc-6-aminohexano *O*-benzyl hydroxamic acid : A mixture of Boc-protected 6-aminohexanoic acid (2.8 g, 12.16 mmol) and 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole (1.97 g, 12.16 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was stirred under nitrogen for 30 min. To it *O*-benzyl hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.94 g, 12.16 mmol) and triethylamine (3.9 g, 36.48 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at RT for 12 h. The product was worked up by washing the dichloromethane solution first with 10% HCl, then with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ and water (10 ml each). Drying (sodium sulphate) and removal of dichloromethane afforded the coupled product as colourless solid (3.5 g, 86%), m.p. 52°; IR (KBr) 3325, 3222, 1680, 1517 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.2–1.6 (6H, m), 1.41 (9H, s), 1.99–2.04 (2H, m), 2.99–3.05 (2H, m), 4.64 (1H, br s), 4.85 (2H, s), 7.27–7.37 (5H, m), 9.22 (1H, br s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 24.8, 26.2, 28.3, 29.6, 32.8, 40.3, 77.9, 79.0, 128.3, 128.4, 129.0, 135.5, 156.1, 170.8.

Boc removal and subsequent debenylation of Boc-6-aminohexano *O*-benzyl hydroxamic acid :

Synthesis of trifluoroacetate salt of 6-aminohexano hydroxamic acid (2) : To a stirred solution of Boc-6-aminohexano *O*-benzyl hydroxamic acid (3.2 g, 9.5 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml), trifluoroacetic acid (6.0 ml) was added and stirred for 8 h. The solvent along with the excess TFA was removed under reduced pressure. The trifluoroacetate salt thus obtained was directly taken for debenylation. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 1.27–1.33 (2H, m), 1.55–1.63 (4H, m), 2.05 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 2.85 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 4.81 (2H, s), 7.30–7.39 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 25.82, 26.69, 28.07, 33.28, 40.46, 78.95, 129.41, 129.59, 130.22, 136.5, 172.47.

The methanolic solution (100 ml) of this salt was hydrogenated over palladium on carbon (1.0 g, 10% Pd on C) at 35 psi for 12 h. Removal of the catalyst (filtration) and the solvent (rotary evaporation) yielded (2.51 g, 96.5%) trifluoroacetate salt of 6-aminohexano hydroxamic acid as white solid, m.p. 127°; IR (KBr) 1646, 1686, 2975, 3238 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 1.36–1.44 (2H, m), 1.59–1.68 (4H, m), 2.11 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 2.90 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 26.02, 26.80, 28.12, 33.30, 40.49, 172.70.

Synthesis of PNIPAM bound hydroxamic acid (3) : To a stirred solution of poly (NIPAM-*c*-VAL) (1) (1.0 g, 1.69 mmol of VAL units) in *t*-butanol (15 ml) was added a solution of triethylamine (340 mg, 3.37 mmol), trifluoroacetate

salt of 6-aminohexano hydroxamic acid (440 mg, 1.69 mmol) in *t*-butanol (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h at 80°. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was redissolved in THF (20 ml). The polymer was precipitated by slow addition of THF solution to hexane (300 ml). The crude precipitated polymer was purified by dissolving in distilled water and precipitating by heating the aqueous solution above the LCST. This operation was repeated one more time and the precipitated polymer was then dried under high vacuum (1.2 g, 97%); IR (KBr) 1658, 3235 cm⁻¹, stretching at 1814 cm⁻¹ completely disappeared. From the spectrophotometric analysis using Fe³⁺ complex, the chelating capacity of the polymer (3) for complete removal of metal was found to be 2.0 mg of Fe³⁺/g of polymer.

Synthesis of chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid (6) : To a chilled and stirred mixture of *O*-benzyl hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2.5 g, 15.67 mmol) and triethyl amine (3.17 g, 31.35 mmol) in dichloromethane (75 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (1.77 g, 15.67 mmol) in dichloromethane (50 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was slowly allowed to come to RT and stirring was continued for additional four hours. The reaction mixture was washed with 5% HCl, brine and water (20 ml each). Drying (anhydrous sodium sulphate) and evaporation of solvent yielded *O*-benzyl chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid (2.71 g, 87% yield) as colourless solid, m.p. 91–93°; IR (KBr) 1646 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 4.02 (2H, s), 4.9 (2H, s), 7.4 (5H, bs), 8.89 (1H, bs).

The above *O*-benzyl protected chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid was debenzylated by stirring the mixture containing 5% Pd/C (500 mg) and the substrate (2.71 g) in ethanol (30 ml) under hydrogen for 12 h at RT. The removal of catalyst and the solvent afforded chloroacetamido hydroxamic acid (1.45 g, 97.5% yield) as colourless solid m.p. 92° (lit.⁶ m.p. 92–93°); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.91 (2H, s), benzylic and aromatic protons completely disappeared.

Synthesis of PNIPAM bound dimethyl aminopropyl diamine (4) : To a stirred solution of poly (NIPAM-*c*-VAL) (1) (5.0 g, 8.46 mmol of VAL units) in *t*-butanol (50 ml), *N,N*-dimethyl aminopropyl diamine (0.863 g, 8.46 mmol) was added and the reaction was stirred under nitrogen at 80° for 8 h. The polymer was purified by precipitating in hexane. The precipitated polymer was further purified by dissolving in water and reprecipitating by heating the aqueous solution. The white precipitated polymer (4); (4.3 g, 73% yield) was then dried under vacuum and it was found to have amine value of 77 from titrating with standard HCl

solution as against theoretical amine value of 80 for 8 : 2 copolymer (4); IR (KBr) 1650, 2945, 3250 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of PNIPAM bound hydroxamic acid (5) : A solution of polymer (4) (3.63 g, 5.24 mmol of *N,N*-dimethyl aminopropyl diamine units) and chloro-acetamido hydroxamic acid (0.6 g, 5.5 mmol) in isopropanol (40 ml) was stirred under nitrogen at 80° for 18 h. The completion of reaction was established by estimating Cl^- using titrimetry. It was found to have 0.39% of chloride ions as against the expected value of 0.42%. On completion of quaternisation the solvent was evaporated using a rotary evaporator and residue was dissolved in water at 25°. The aqueous solution was heated to 50° and the off-white purified polymer (5) thus obtained was dried under vacuum and powdered before using for chelation study (3.8 g, 90%); IR (KBr) 1643, 1669, 2976, 3300 cm^{-1} . From the

spectrophotometric analysis using Fe^{3+} complex, the chelating capacity of the polymer (3) for quantitative removal of metal was found to be 1.8 mg of Fe^{3+} /g of polymer.

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